

Looking beyond the boundary: Modelling constituency level voting behaviour in the 2024 UK General Election

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Summary

When modelling areal data, an intrinsic conditional autoregressive (ICAR) component is often used to capture spatial autocorrelation across boundaries. A standard assumption of such models is a global variance parameter, meaning all areas undergo the same degree of spatial smoothing. We propose allowing this variance parameter to change, reflecting different degrees of spatial cohesion in different regions. We demonstrate an application using voting data from the 2024 UK General Election. By comparing the marginal likelihoods of a series of models representing different hypothesised spatial processes, we find that this novel approach is the most plausible model for three of the four largest parties.

KEYWORDS: UK Elections, Spatial Regression, ICAR Modelling, Spatial Cohesion, Bayes Factors

1 Introduction

When modelling spatial data, it is well understood that there is a tendency for nearby data points to be more similar than distant ones. When working with areal data, the intrinsic conditional autoregressive (ICAR) structure is commonly used as a smoother to capture this process, where each unit's value is an average of that of its neighbours plus some random variation (Besag & Kooperberg, 1995). It is also possible that groups of data points can be seen as comprising regions, where a certain difference between and similarity within region is to be expected. This structure fits into the hierarchical modelling framework. These two structures can be fit individually or in combination to model one or more hypothesised spatial processes.

We propose a technique which combines group structures and an autoregressive component in a different way. In ICAR models, the strength of smoothing is controlled by a single variance parameter for the entire area. Rather than capturing region differences with a set of random

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effects, we instead incorporate group variation in the ICAR process itself by allowing the variance parameter to vary by region, meaning that the strength of the spatial smoothing differs across groups. Regions with lower variance exhibit stronger spatial smoothing (smaller variability among neighbours), while regions with higher variance allow for greater heterogeneity in the random effects within that region. This can capture differences in spatial cohesion which may better account for the process than region-specific random intercepts..

This method will be demonstrated using data from the 2024 UK General Election in England. We model the vote count of the four largest parties (Labour, Conservative, Liberal Democrat and Reform UK) using Bayesian Poisson generalised linear models. We observe that, having controlled for some socio-economic variables, the winner and runner-up from the previous election and the size of the majority, there still remains some unaccounted-for spatial structure. Six models of increasing complexity are then fitted for each of the four parties, ranging from those which contain only one spatial process to others with combined processes. We also fit our novel approach allowing the variance of the ICAR structure to change by region. We then rank these models according to marginal likelihood and determine which is most plausible for each party, given the voting data. In our example, we find that the novel approach is the best model for three of the four parties, while the best model for the Liberal Democrats is a combination of individual region random effects and a standard ICAR structure.

2 Data Used

The two data sources in this study are the 2021 census (Office for National Statistics, 2021) and the results of the 2024 and 2019 General Elections (House of Commons Library, 2024). The percentage vote share for each party is shown in Figure 1 (a-d). The three census socio-economic covariates included in the model are mapped in Figure 1 (e-g). These three variables are a subset of those considered by Beecham et al. (2018) in a study of voting behaviour in the Brexit referendum. Each is closely correlated with and can serve as a proxy for a number of other related socio-demographic variables. The variables used to account for the status quo ante are also shown (Figure 1 (h-j)). These are the first and second place parties in 2019, and the marginality of each seat expressed as the majority which the winning party attained as a proportion of total constituency votes. The effect of marginality is allowed to vary according to runner-up party.

3 Methods

If Y_i is the number of votes cast for a party in constituency i , its likelihood is modelled as

$$Y_i \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_i),$$

where

$$\log(\mu_i) = \mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta} + \text{offset}_i$$

Figure 1: Vote counts and explanatory variables mapped as hexagons of equal size, while still approximating relative position. This overcomes the problem of invisibility arising from some small, densely populated urban constituencies. In later maps, where a more precise idea of relative position and contiguity is an important consideration (as is the case when exploring neighbourhood relationships) maps will be shown in regular projection.

The offset term is the log of the total votes per constituency to account for different exposures, and the $\mathbf{x}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}$ component contains the control variables. Each model adds additional regional or constituency level effects (or both) to this basic structure, as summarised in Table 1. Flat priors were used for all $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ parameters. For sampling efficiency, we found the following prior to be most appropriate for the variance parameters:

$$\sigma \sim \text{Student-t}(3, 0, 2.5), \quad \sigma > 0$$

A standard ICAR effect, ϕ_i , for each constituency conditional on that of its neighbours is captured by the following prior,

$$p(\phi_i \mid \phi_j, j \neq i, \sigma) \sim \text{Normal} \left(\frac{\sum_{i \sim j} \phi_j}{d_{i,i}}, \frac{\sigma^2}{d_{i,i}} \right)$$

where $d_{i,i}$ is the number of neighbours for constituency i , and $i \sim j$ refers to pairs of neighbouring constituencies.

The novel approach uses this structure:

$$p(\phi_{ik} \mid \phi_j, j \neq i, \sigma_k) \sim \text{Normal} \left(\frac{\sum_{i \sim j} \phi_{jk}}{d_{i,i}}, \frac{\sigma_k^2}{d_{i,i}} \right)$$

where the variance σ_k^2 can change for each region, k . In both cases, a soft sum-to-zero constraint is applied to ensure identifiability:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.001 \cdot N)$$

Models 1-5 are fit in R using the `brms` package. Model 6 is fit using `rstan` (Stan Development Team, 2024) by a modification of the Stan code of model 3, as generated using the `brms` function `get_stancode()`.

4 Results

4.1 Most plausible model

To determine which of these six models is the most plausible for each party given this data, we use Bayes factors which compare the likelihood of the data under two competing models. The marginal likelihood of each model was estimated using the `bridgesampling` package in R (Gronau & Singmann, 2017).

Table 1: Spatial processes in models.

model	constituency spatial effect	region spatial effect
1	—	independent region random effects
2	—	region random effects from common distribution
3	ICAR process	—
4	ICAR process	independent region random effects
5	ICAR process	region random effects from common distribution
6	ICAR process	varying icar sd by region

Table 2 shows the models ranked according to increasing log marginal likelihood for each party, and the Bayes factor of each model compared to the next most plausible above it. For the first three sets of models in Table 2 (Conservative, Labour and Reform UK), the same models are favoured in the same order of plausibility. The most plausible is model 6, that with an ICAR component whose standard deviation is allowed to vary by region. The evidence in favour of this model over its closest competitor is in each case classified as *extreme*, according to a scale suggested by Lee and Wagenmakers (2014).

The situation is quite different for the Liberal Democrats. Here, the most plausible model is model 4 which is *anecdotally* preferred to model 3 but *extremely* favoured over model 6. This is a model which combines a standard constant variance ICAR process at constituency level with independent region effects.

This means that we have strong evidence that this novel form of ICAR structure can, in certain situations, provide a more plausible mechanism for the underlying spatial processes than other more commonly used models, with Bayes factors being useful to identify when this is appropriate.

4.2 Spatial posteriors

The ‘best’ model for three of the parties (Conservative, Labour and Reform UK) allows for varying spatial cohesion. Figure 2 (a-c) shows the mean posterior ICAR structure across regions from this model while Figure 2 (d-f) shows different degrees of cohesion. London shows low spatial cohesion for all three parties. Aside from London, Reform UK votes show high cohesion (low standard deviation) across England. For Labour, the highest levels of cohesion are in the north whereas the opposite is the case for the Conservatives.

Turning to Figure 3, we show spatial posteriors from model 4, the most plausible model for the Liberal Democrats. The global standard deviation parameter shown in Figure 3 (d) is higher than that which was estimated for the other parties in their optimal models. Regional variability is accounted for by independently distributed random effects (Figure 3 (a-b)).

Table 2: Comparison of models across parties, ranked by increasing log marginal likelihood, alongside the degree of evidence for successive model improvement provided by Bayes factor comparison. Models are preferred in the same sequence for Conservative, Labour and Reform UK, but differently for Liberal Democrat. The optimal model for each party appears in bold. While the varying standard deviation structure (model 6) is the most plausible for three parties, the situation is different for the Liberal Democrats where a combination of independent region effects and an ICAR component (model 4) is preferred.

model	constituency level effects	region level effects	log marg lik	bayes factor	evidence
Conservative					
1	—	independent distributions	-83366.370	—	—
2	—	common distribution	-83357.009	12000	extreme
5	ICAR	common distribution	-4859.908	>1e+8	extreme
4	ICAR	independent distributions	-4823.069	>1e+8	extreme
3	ICAR	—	-4814.148	7300	extreme
6	ICAR	varying ICAR sd	-4808.231	370	extreme
Labour					
1	—	independent distributions	-178671.783	—	—
2	—	common distribution	-178667.283	90	very strong
5	ICAR	common distribution	-5449.327	>1e+8	extreme
4	ICAR	independent distributions	-5215.785	>1e+8	extreme
3	ICAR	—	-5209.243	670	extreme
6	ICAR	varying ICAR sd	-5172.219	>1e+8	extreme
Reform UK					
1	—	independent distributions	-42318.162	—	—
2	—	common distribution	-42315.110	22	strong
5	ICAR	common distribution	-4274.228	>1e+8	extreme
4	ICAR	independent distributions	-4271.509	15	strong
3	ICAR	—	-4261.840	16000	extreme
6	ICAR	varying ICAR sd	-4250.178	160000	extreme
Liberal Democrat					
2	—	common distribution	-258507.879	—	—
1	—	independent distributions	-258506.495	4.1	moderate
5	ICAR	common distribution	-4840.705	>1e+8	extreme
6	ICAR	varying ICAR sd	-4707.882	>1e+8	extreme
3	ICAR	—	-4693.747	>1e+8	extreme
4	ICAR	independent distributions	-4693.208	1.7	anecdotal

Figure 2: (a-c) Mean posterior of ICAR component of model 6 for Conservatives, Labour and Reform UK respectively, (d-f) mean posterior value of standard deviation component from model 6 for each party, varying by region.

Figure 3: (a) Posterior distribution of region effects for Liberal Democrats from model 4, (b) the mean value for each region effect, (c) the posterior mean of the ICAR component, and (d) the posterior standard deviation parameter of the ICAR component.

5 Conclusions

This method of allowing spatial cohesion to vary by region has wider application potential than just to voting data. In epidemiological modelling, for example, it might be desirable to allow the intensity of the spread of disease to be similarly variable by region. Rather than using region random effects, perhaps the process could be better captured by focussing only on the spatially smoothed ICAR component but allowing its degree of smoothness to vary. This idea could also be applied to studies of crime, social inequality, public health, environmental issues, ecology and housing markets. Within each of these areas, the meaning of the varying standard deviation of the ICAR structure would have its own interpretation.

It is this area of interpretation which may be one of the main limitations of this model. A combination of hierarchical effects and a spatially smooth process lends itself to a more standard and less complicated narrative than discussion of spatial cohesion. However, the explicit measure of spatial cohesion which this model provides may be of interest to test specific theories. Also, if the more complex model is deemed more plausible, this can raise questions about the simpler model's assumptions.

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